

**INTERPRETATION OF THE HUMAN HEART IN THE POEM BY
ABDULLAH ORIPOV**

Chirchik state pedagogical university of research

Kodirova Guzal

Annotation: These article In the poet's lyricism, opening the psyche of the hero, in the image of the cries of the heart, metaphors, symbols become the leading artistic medium. The poet person free transcribes into the language of symbols the exclamations of the ideas of freedom of the nation and independence of the motherland.

Keywords: society, person, troubles, wait, athlete, victory, expect, return.

Introduction

It is well known to all of us that a society in which a person enters a structure can be compared to an athlete running a long distance. Ahead of the athlete is waiting for a victory, which is expected in return for his troubles. To reach it, the athlete requires art and professionalism, along with Labor. In the sciences of aesthetics and philosophy, in the sciences of literary and Religious Studies, a person is defined as a breed whose heart, first of all, is elevated to the level of humanity. However, it turns out that he is not the one who has lost men and made dye.

The main of the results

The freedom of a person is in his heart. By the way, since his soul, his mind is angle, is always in motion. The individual seeks to fight whenever he stands on the side of Justice. As he fought for the freedom of the oppressed people, he would not agree with his nation's rule over others. The individual is also the one who breaks through the shell of his selfishness. He is the one who is only ashamed to think to himself, and finally begins to feel the need for concern about others. Therefore, in the history of our literature, great breeds passed, they were worthless persons if they took a lesson. It is the same fact that poets have changed the path of an entire

nation. And in his call will be embodied thousands of national destinies. Poets see the world in a different way. Will be in action with goodness and goodness. It requires purity of heart, mental calmness, died in the path of the nation's perspective. And proves and teaches to live like that.

The poet who still excites the hearts of Uzbek literature-he has letters that are just as bright as the literature of the 20th century, the breeds that have been plunged into the future are very rarely found in other times. In Particular, Kadiri, Chulpan, Oybek, Qahhor, H.Olimjon, Zulfiya, Mirtemir, O.Yakubov. There are rightful and bright stars of our nation, such as P.Kadyrov, who are not only still the basis and deep School of lesson for recent literature, but also as similar, a dedicated teacher, in the maturation of the youth of the independence period with such happy feelings. Hundreds of charming poems by the singer of happiness and joy Hamid Olimjon have a great influence on the work of emerging poets. This resulted in A.Oripov, E.Vohidov, Sh.Rahman, U.Azim, of poets, such as X.Davron, grew up. In the work of this generation, there is exactly a simple and sincere tone, lines, the roots of which go back to the work of the above poets. Poetry is in the midst of updates. Thirst for innovation gives light to the soul of a person, hope for tomorrow. Consequently, there are people who, for some reason, shrug their poetry in the era of independence, say that it has come to life a little, simplified, but a different mood will appear in a person who persistently looks at its essence:

In ancient tales
Describing the world,
Language takes a lot
Three-headed dragon.
To the dragon in fact
Why do you need three heads?
One who swallows prey
The two stems are alert.

Man is not a dragon,

Only one has a head.

All trade to him

Capacity to need.[1;23]

In the poet's lyricism, opening the psyche of the hero, in the image of the cries of the heart, metaphors, symbols become the leading artistic medium. The poet person free transcribes into the language of symbols the exclamations of the ideas of freedom of the nation and independence of the motherland. It is permissible to realize psychologism in the poet's poetry in the way of landscapes of a flood of feelings born in the heart, influenced by nature, social reality and life phenomena, an interpretation of thoughts in the way of states, moods, irradiated in the consciousness-thinking of the lyrical hero. Therefore, U. Normatov noted: " the art of being able to vividly depict life events, human experiences by conveying thought, the idea of the work to the reader in a simple, understandable way is one of the main factors indicating the level of skill of any creator". In reality, in the poems of the poet, skill at the level of art is clearly known to the reader.

Everything passes, career, glory-he is also a knight,

The sweet is sweet and the bitter is sweet and the bitter is bitter.

One day it will be more, and the unequal sun face too,

Only the people live, only the people who stay.[2;90]

It is known that in the next period there will be a real example of a lesson for the people the desire to create the image of men has become much stronger. We will witness that this situation is clearly manifested in the poem "people" by the poet. Literary Critic. As U. Normatov noted," ... the need for works in which the image of a strong, beautiful person is created has intensified, especially when our homeland has gained independence, the people have achieved their destiny, a fuller manifestation of their self." Indeed, This poem by A.Oripov was written in 1994, that is, it was written during the period after independence when everyone remained preoccupied with himself for a certain time. In it, the fact that everyone

thinks of the people without thinking about themselves, their arms, their dreams, the fulfillment of their sorrows are expressed in the description of the poem, in a unique style. The poem particularly emphasizes that the lyrical hero is sometimes shaken with age in the eye, and sometimes with laughter on the face-he is circling. But in this universe, only the people will remain, he will live forever, and the rest will pass by one, like the passengers in the caravan.

Look at your name-my cotton, are you,
Loppi deya won-my blood, are you,
My throne, who hit the head on the prison, are you?!
Only the people live, only the people who stay.[3;74]

Taking a look at our history, the history of our literature mature poet-he, we are again convinced that we are the descendants of the great talent, seeing the examples of creativity of our creators. But the owners of such talent became victims of the times in the cuttings of life. Hence, in the excerpt taken, Zim is referred to the policy of" cotton "work," Uzbek work "and" kulak", which fell on the head of the Uzbek people in the 20th century through the exclamations" my cotton", " my blood", " my wood". Especially in 1937, 1950s, slanderous stones were thrown at our people's favorite poet-U writers, they were executed and exiled on charges of treason, thanks to the "Uzbek affair" of the 1980s, many of our people's dear children suffered, the poet reflected in his own way through these verses, the main reason for which the fact that at that time it was difficult to tell the truth directly,

Do not forget about the great-grandfathers who gave their lives in the jungles,
Do not forget about the momos who plucked bread.
Do not forget the prayers that faith has given faith,
Only the people live, only the people who stay.[4;45]

The poet's poems" Uzbekman", " secret universe", " Navruz", " Sea for Uzbekistan", " Uzbekistan century", like the poem" The People", have a spirit of

patriotism, devotion to the motherland. Because a real creator will be a selfless and faithful child of his people. It is considered an achievement inherent in all times, all peoples, all space. Although the size is small, even in these verses, thousands of years of history, joy and oysters of our people are incredibly natural, deeply reflected. The reason is that we have long been the cradle of a great nation, a mighty Land of culture, and we have no right to forget the people who have built strong beliefs and brought up geniuses. After all, our famous poet. As E.Vohidov noted, " a person is a person who knows good deeds, high beliefs. For the poet, the question of love for the motherland comes first" in the poem above is given mainly the definition of el, a verb-like drawing typical of the Uzbek nation-but, it is no one without the land. Therefore, the homeland of the nation has been photographed together wonderfully. Because, for the poet himself, the motherland of falsehood is that breast kerish iodine thing, the poet simply does not smear the paper with a mouthwash. He came to life from the heart of the finished verses, from the poet's chest. Hence A.Oripov's poems are characterized by mean and jealousy.

In the poems above, we have mentioned the greatness of our nation, and among us are those who, alas, "do not say that Rice will not be without dates." In the poem "educator" by A.Oripov, there are such educators in teaching education in our country that they, having trained naive mistresses of poor quality, again considered themselves very "intelligent" people. Singing from such a state, he puts aside his personal experiences and goes out into the field as if he is telling someone what belongs to him. So is it possible for the poet's heart to openly turn to us, and the levelless educator to make others level? The question enchants, excites, captivates with its lines, which conquer the heart with its gaze, captivates with all its complexity. In this range, the sincerity of both the poet and the reader is not undermined.

Abdullah Oripov's "yara" are outspoken poets. It can be advanced to the fullest in similar lines that he has nothing to hide. Therefore, the poet devotes himself to always maintaining his personality, discovering new-new meanings. The

dedication, however, becomes dye in literature. He, like others, begins to live with suffering. Sufferings fill in, torment, connect their confessions to their students through the criteria of upbringing. With the fourfold lines, he gives the reader his presence. Truth and Justice consider chanting to be self-pride and duty. Both motherland and beloved are friends with him-he is as dear as brothers and leaves and trees. It is he who can also feel the value of this nobility. In addition, she explains this to her student. As Carl Jung, a major 20th-century psychologist, said that "without a person himself, a person cannot raise an individual", the acquaintance of the educator himself with breeds that have risen to the height of personality and their works can give extraordinary positive results.

Conclusion

In general, the poems of Abdullah Oripov are among the best examples of the current Uzbek poetry, in which the national customs of the Uzbek people and the colorful polish of the human soul were embodied in beautiful charms and images. His poems remained lifelong among the people. The poet left himself a huge beautiful garden, in which ripe fruits in the garden will undoubtedly delight the future generation for several years with its sweet taste.

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